

MORPHOFUNCTIONAL STATE OF JUDOKA ATHLETES FOR THE PREPARATION
OF PROFESSIONAL TEACHING ACTIVITIES

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Abstract: the article reveals that sport helps a child develop harmoniously, strengthens the nervous system, immunity, and has a positive effect on the health of the body as a whole. In addition, playing sports teaches a child discipline, builds character, develops willpower, and the ability to set goals and achieve them. Physical education is necessary for a person at all periods of his life. In childhood and adolescence, they contribute to the harmonious development of the body. In adults, they improve the morphofunctional state, increase performance and maintain health. Any physical exercise improves heart function. Sport brings positive emotions and discipline to a person's life. Exercising strengthens the body, improves muscle memory and coordination.

Key words: athlete development/ ability to develop/ interaction with the profession/ athlete's activities/ chosen profession.

МОРФОФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНОЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ СПОРТСМЕНОВ – ДЗЮДОИСТОВ
К ПОДГОТОВКЕ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ - ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЙ
ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ

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Аннотация: в статье раскрывается спорт помогает ребенку гармонично развиваться, укрепляет нервную систему, иммунитет, положительно сказывается на здоровье организма в целом. Кроме того, занятия спортом приучают ребенка к дисциплине, формируют характер, развивают силу воли, умение ставить цели и достигать их. Занятия физической культурой необходимы человеку во все периоды его жизни. В детском и юношеском возрасте они способствуют слаженному развитию организма. У взрослых улучшают морфофункциональное состояние, увеличивают работоспособность и сохраняют здоровье. Занятия любыми физическими упражнениями улучшают работу сердца. Спорт приносит в жизнь человека положительные эмоции и дисциплину. Занятия спортом укрепляют тело, улучшают мышечную память и координацию.

Ключевые слова: развитие спортсмена/ способность к развитию/ взаимодействию с профессией/ деятельность спортсмена/ избранная профессия.

Participating in any kind of physical activity improves heart function, reduces the risk of diabetes by lowering blood sugar levels, and also regulates stress levels. Sport brings positive emotions and discipline to a person's life. Exercising strengthens the body, improves muscle memory and coordination. It is sport that develops such personality qualities as determination, patience, strength, endurance, perseverance, respect for oneself and the people around you. Any person can play sports, the main thing is desire.

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Promotes the development of strong-willed qualities and self-organization. Teaches you to take a blow, to correctly experience not only victories, but also defeats. During classes, a person develops the important ability to analyze the causes of failures, work on mistakes, and overcome the fear of failure. And in the end - to win. Physical activity directly affects a person's psycho-emotional state. During sports, we begin to move actively, blood circulation increases and breathing quickens. More oxygen reaches the brain cells, which means the feeling of fatigue and drowsiness disappears. Sports activity develops the most important personal qualities, not only such as endurance, strength, dexterity of movement, but also determination, perseverance, responsibility, collectivism, and determination.

At its core, physical culture has expedient motor activity in the form of physical exercises that allow one to effectively develop the necessary skills and abilities, physical abilities, and optimize health and performance. Sport has amazing properties. It can unite people, introduce them to each other, strengthen health, character, and even improve the mental abilities of the people who engage in it. Sports develop a person's skills such as speed, agility, reaction, coordination, endurance, patience and strength.

Physical culture is an organic part of universal human culture, its special independent area. At the same time, this is "a mythical process and the result of human activity, a means and method of physical improvement of the individual. Physical culture influences the vital aspects of an individual, received in the form of inclinations that are transmitted genetically and develop during life under the influence of upbringing, activity and the environment. Physical culture satisfies social needs in communication, play, entertainment, and in some forms of personal self-expression through socially active useful activities. At its core, physical culture has expedient motor activity in the form of physical exercises that allow one to effectively develop the necessary skills and abilities, physical abilities, and optimize health and performance. Physical culture is represented by a set of material and spiritual values. The first include sports facilities, equipment, special equipment, sports equipment, and medical support. The latter include information, works of art, various sports, games, sets of physical exercises, ethical standards governing human behavior in the process of physical education and sports activities, etc. In developed forms, physical culture produces aesthetic values (physical education parades, sports demonstrations speeches, etc.). The result of activities in physical culture is physical fitness and the degree of perfection of motor skills, a high level of development of vital forces, sports achievements, moral, aesthetic, and intellectual development.

So, physical culture should be considered as a special kind of cultural activity, the results of which are useful for society and the individual. In social life in the system of education, upbringing, and the sphere of organization of work, everyday life, healthy recreation, physical culture manifests its educational, educational, health, economic and general cultural significance, contributes to the emergence of such a social movement as the physical culture movement, i.e. joint activities of people to use, disseminate and enhance the values of physical culture.

Included in the education and upbringing system, starting from preschool institutions, it characterizes the basis of people's physical fitness - the acquisition of a fund of vital motor skills and abilities, the diversified development of physical abilities. Its important elements are the "school" of movement, the system of gymnastic exercises and the Rules for their implementation, with the help of which the child develops the ability to differentially control movements, the ability to coordinate them in different combinations; a system of exercises for the rational use of forces

when moving in space (the main methods of walking, running, swimming, skating, skiing, etc.) when overcoming obstacles, throwing, lifting and carrying heavy objects; “school” of the ball (playing volleyball, basketball, handball, football, tennis, etc.). Physical development is a biological process of formation, changes in the natural morphological and functional properties of the body during a person’s life (length, body weight, chest circumference, vital capacity of the lungs, maximum oxygen consumption, strength, speed, endurance, flexibility, agility, etc.) .

The process of physical development also obeys the law of age gradation. Therefore, it is possible to intervene in this process in order to control it only taking into account the characteristics and capabilities of the body at different age periods; formation and growth, the highest development of forms and functions, aging. In addition, physical development is associated with the law of unity of the organism and the environment and depends on human living conditions, including the geographical environment. Therefore, when choosing means and methods of physical education, it is necessary to take into account the influence of these laws. Physical development is closely related to human health. Health acts as a leading factor that determines not only the harmonious development of a young person, but also the success of mastering a profession, the fruitfulness of his future professional activity, which constitutes overall well-being in life. Thanks to professional applied physical education, the prerequisites are created for the successful mastery of a particular profession and the effective performance of work. In production, these are introductory gymnastics, physical education breaks, physical education minutes, post-work rehabilitation exercises, etc. The content and composition of professional applied physical education means, the order of their use are determined by the characteristics of the labor process. In conditions of military service, it acquires the features of military-professional physical culture.

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАННЫЕ ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ:

1. Тураев, М. М. (2022). Оздоровительная физическая культура её основы и инновационные технологии. *Science and Education*, 3(4), 1102-1108.
2. Тураев, М. М. Образование и воспитание в сфере физической культуры-особенности повышения эффективности использования национальных ценностей. Центр научных публикаций (buxdu. uz), 8(8).
3. Тураев, М. М. (2022, November). Организация проектных технологий на уроках физической культуры: 10.53885/edinres. 2022.61. 66.124 Тураев Махмуд Мухамедович Бухарский государственный университет, преподаватель. In Научно-практическая конференция (pp. 975-978).
4. Тураев, М. М. (2024). Сравнительная педагогика физической культуры, отрасль знания спорта и учебная дисциплина. *Science and Education*, 5(2), 335-340.
5. Тураев, М. М. (2024). Педагогическая технология в спортивной гимнастике, системы имитационного моделирования. *Science and Education*, 5(1), 332-337.
6. Тураев, М. М., Баймурадов, Р. С., & Файзиев, Я. З. (2020). Интерактивные методы физического воспитания в вузах. *Педагогическое образование и наука*, (3), 132-135.
7. Хамраев, И. Т., Курбанов, Д. И., & Тураев, М. М. (2021). Принципы современной педагогической подготовки. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(2), 899-907.
8. Тураев, М. М. (2021). Методы преподавания физического образования и их важные аспекты. *Проблемы науки*, (2 (61)), 35-37.

9. Тураев, М. М. (2021). Повышение эффективности физического воспитания студентов с помощью компьютерных технологий. Вестник науки и образования, (5-3 (118)), 99-102.
10. MM Turaev, BJ Boltayeva, SJ Razokova. The importace of phisical education and phisical culture at schools. Вестник науки и образования 1 (2-2 (122)), 34-37
11. Тураев, М. М. Теория и методика физической культуры. Учебное пособие, 1(1), 220.
12. Тураев, М. М. Методы преподавания социального образования и их важные аспекты. Проблемы науки, 35-37.
13. Маъмуров, Б. Б., & Тураев, М. М. (2023). Актуальные проблемы подготовки специалистов физического воспитания и спорта в современных условиях. In Проблемы и перспективы развития спортивного образования, науки и практики (pp. 134-142).
14. Тураев, М. М. (2022, November). Организация проектных технологий на уроках физической культуры: 10.53885/edinres. 2022.61. 66.124 Тураев Махмуд Мухамедович Бухарский государственный университет, преподаватель. In Научно-практическая конференция (pp. 975-978).
15. Баймурадов, Р. С., Файзиев, Я. З., & Тураев, М. М. (2019). Психологический анализ личности спортсмена. Педагогическое образование и наука, (6), 144-148.
16. Тураев, М. М. (2024). Сравнительная педагогика физической культуры, отрасль знания спорта и учебная дисциплина. Science and Education, 5(2), 335-340.
17. MM Тураев, ЭЮ Исломов. Организация и проведение оздоровительных занятий для людей пожилого возраста. Физическая культура. Рекреация. Спорт, 470-476
18. Тураев, М. М. (2024). Педагогическая технология в спортивной гимнастике, системы имитационного моделирования. Science and Education, 5(1), 332-337.
19. М Тураев. Important factors for the organization of medical groups in physical education. Центр научных публикаций (buxdu. Uz) 8 (8)
20. М Тураев. Содержание процесса организации оздоровительных занятий для людей пожилого возраста. Центр научных публикаций (buxdu. Uz) 7 (7)
21. М Тураев. Actual problems of teaching physical education at school. Центр научных публикаций (buxdu. uz) 23 (23)
22. MM Turayev, BJQ Boltayeva. Og'ma xulq-atvor o'rganish mahsuli sifatida. Science and Education 3 (4), 1694-1701
23. MM Тураев. Теория и методика физической культуры. Вестник Бухарского государственного университета 1, 1 - 276
24. MM Тураев. Манипуляционное управление спортсменов - легкоатлетов спортивными модуляционно разработанными методами, приёмами. Science and Education 5 (3), 445-451
25. Alibek Botirovich Jo'Rayev (2024). **Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida harakatli o'yinlar orqali jismoniy sifatlarni rivojlantirish (kurash)**
26. АБ Жураев. Обучения к нагрузкам физической подготовки как деятельность подготовке школьников. Science and Education 5 (2), 574-579

27. Рахмон Равшанович Латипов (2024). Школьная аксиологическая подготовка учителя физической культуры на современном этапе эволюции. *Science and Education*, 5 (1), 299-304.

28. Рахмон Равшанович Латипов (2024). Философия спортивного искусства и образования в подготовке педагога-физической культуры. *Science and Education*, 5 (1), 292-298.

29. Latipov, R., & Ramazanov, M. (2023). Jismoniy madaniyat ta'lim yo'nalishi talabalarini kasbiy pedagogik madaniyatni tarbiyalashda tajriba-sinov ishlarining samaradorlik darajasi. *Молодые ученые*, 1(21), 37–40.

30. AA Abdullayev, SA Pirnazarov. maktab yoshgacha bolalarning suzish sportiga bo'lgan munosabati. *Academic research in educational sciences* 3 (4), 306-310

